

ARTWIN

INDUSTRY & CONSTRUCTION
4.0 SOLUTIONS

Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan

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Project Information

TITLE	ARtwin - An AR cloud and digital twins solution for industry and construction 4.0
DURATION	October 2019 – September 2022 (36 months)
WEBSITE	artwin-project.eu
COORDINATOR	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC
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PROJECT OVERVIEW	ARtwin aims at improving productivity and product quality, by deploying an ARCloud platform that will offer a wide variety of cutting-edge AR-based services to industry and construction 4.0.
CONSORTIUM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC www.qplan-intl.gr – Greece 2. B-COM http://www.b-com.com – France 3. SIEMENS AKTIENGESELLSCHAFT https://new.siemens.com/global/en.html – Germany 4. CESKE VYSOKE UCENI TECHNICKE V PRAZE http://www.cvut.cz/en - Czech Republic 5. NOKIA BELL LABS FRANCE http://www.bell-labs.com/ – France 6. HOLO-INDUSTRIE 4.0 SOFTWARE GMBH http://www.holo-light.com/contact.html - Germany 7. ARTEFACTO SAS http://www.artefacto-ar.com/en/ – France

Executive Summary

This document constitutes the first version of the Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan (DACP) of the ARTwin project.

ARTwin is a Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action aiming to develop and introduce an easily deployable platform that enables the design and maintenance of highly accurate digital representations of real environments, be they factories or construction sites (Digital Twin or BIM), that are updated in real time and allow for the deployment of high quality interactive services, well-tailored to the requirements of Industry and Construction 4.0.

The document describes the overall awareness raising strategy, the management and monitoring of the dissemination activities and the partners' responsibilities in this respect. It includes specific actions and activities that will be carried out by the ARTwin consortium members in order to ensure success and maximum publicity for the project and its results. With that said, this deliverable outlines:

1. **What to disseminate** - Chapter two is devoted to the basic project-related information that will be conveyed throughout the project.
2. **To whom** - Chapter three presents the key stakeholder groups that will serve as the main audiences for the project's dissemination, awareness raising and communication campaign.
3. **By what means** - Chapter four includes all the channels and tools that will be utilized by project partners in order to successfully implement the dissemination activities.
4. **When** - Chapter five provides a time frame to ensure that the timing of the dissemination activities is appropriate, during the lifespan of the project and beyond.
5. **Monitoring of the process** - Chapter six identifies the indicators to measure success on the dissemination, awareness raising and communication actions, enabling partners to refine efforts and actions over the course of the project.

This deliverable corresponds to the Task 6.1 "Dissemination and communication strategy, plan and activities" of Work Package (WP) 6 "Dissemination, communication and exploitation". The DACP will be updated at least once more in March 2021 (M18 of project duration), but ad hoc revisions will also be made, if necessary, according to the progress of the project.

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1. Introduction

This report, titled “**D6.1: Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan**” (DACP), aims to design the strategy, plan and activities to be implemented under the ARtwin project, with a view to maximizing the project’s visibility and impact. With that in mind, this deliverable outlines the approach to (i) effectively communicate the project and disseminate its results, (ii) guide the partners in planning and implementing their individual dissemination activities and (iii) continuously monitor the efficiency and the timely planning of the actions. In this respect, the deliverable aims to:

- Describe the types of dissemination tools to be implemented and the required actions and resources.
- Define responsibilities among partners.
- Summarize the internal monitoring, evaluation and reporting of dissemination activities.
- Provide an indicative timetable/ work planning of promotion activities during the project.

With the above in mind, the “Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan” is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1 - Introduction:** Provides introductory information with respect to the DACP and its structure.
- **Chapter 2 - Dissemination assets:** Presents the main project’s assets to be disseminated throughout the period of the grant and beyond.
- **Chapter 3 - Target groups:** Presents the key stakeholder groups that will serve as the main audiences for the project’s dissemination, awareness raising and communication campaign.
- **Chapter 4 - Channels and tools:** Encompasses all the channels and tools that will be utilized for the dissemination activities of the project.
- **Chapter 5 - Time plan:** Provides the timeframe for the communication, awareness raising and dissemination activities of the project partners.
- **Chapter 6 - Performance indicators and monitoring:** Identifies the indicators to measure success on the dissemination actions, enabling partners to refine efforts over the course of the project.
- **Chapter 7 - Conclusions:** Pertains to the conclusions of the Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan, as well as the way forward.

The Annexes include the dedicated forms for the dissemination activities list (i.e. dissemination activities, publications, external events), the informative lists (i.e. future events, stakeholders engaged, relevant initiatives, EU dissemination channels), as well as the EU requirements on communication and dissemination of results and finally, a template to be used when reporting an event that is organized by a member of the Consortium.

This deliverable will be updated at least once more in M18, providing a more detailed analysis of the dissemination actions and plans, as the project evolves and dissemination activities become more meaningful. Ad-hoc revisions might also be made, if considered necessary, during the project life span.

2. Dissemination assets

The assets that follow will be disseminated by all partners with a view to maximizing the project’s impact and visibility. This information will be conveyed in a meaningful way and well-tailored to each stakeholder group (to be described further below).

- **Vision and aim** - The vision, aim and strategic objectives of the project will be widely disseminated along with all the conceptual aspects of the project, namely the whole project concept, its innovative characteristics, its impact both in industry and construction, etc.
- **News** – News pertaining to the technical achievements of the project, like the Artwin platform and its services, will be highly communicated once these tools are developed.
- **Events** - The events organised by the project, namely the two workshops focusing on end-users and the Final Conference will be widely disseminated to attract stakeholders from the project’s target groups, along with the events that the partners participate in (e.g. to present their scientific papers).
- **Scientific knowledge** - The scientific knowledge that derives from the project, in the form of public deliverables and scientific publications, will be promoted in journals with high impact factor, in major scientific and industrial events, as well as through widely used online platforms and repositories.
- **Main exploitable assets** - Key project’s assets, as depicted in table 1, will be disseminated as widely as possible in order to stimulate the interest of prospective end-customers and nurture the ground for their post-project rollout.

Table 1. ARTwin’s main exploitable assets

ARTwin’s main assets
The ARTwin platform integrating the project’s interactive technologies providing the following services:
- Development and updating of a unified global map of the factory/construction site
- Localisation service to track AR devices
- Development and real-time updating of a 3D Digital Twin/BIM of a factory/construction site
- AR Remote Rendering service for displaying complex 3D models on low resources AR devices
ARTwin Business Model(s) and Plan(s)
Research data and scientific publications stemming from the research, development and pilot demonstration and evaluation activities, offering meaningful utility to stakeholders from the research and academic community
The ARTwin brand and community created and enhanced throughout the duration of the project, facilitating the dissemination and commercial exploitation of the project’s assets
Public project reports / deliverables

3. Target groups

The key stakeholders of ARTwin can be segmented in the target groups outlined in table 2 below.

Table 2. ARTwin’s main target groups

ARTwin’s target stakeholder groups	
Industrial stakeholders (Industry 4.0/ Construction)	Businesses that may serve as end-users of the ARTwin platform and their personnel
	- Workers in industrial and construction environments
	- Managers tasked with the design of work flows as well as with operations / resource planning (e.g. shop floor/technical managers and planners, etc.)
	- Decision-makers in leading industrial businesses that have the potential to adopt the solutions of ARTwin (such CEOs, VPs, high-level HR executives, etc.)
	Businesses who may develop their own applications based on the ARTwin platform, or businesses that may serve as partners / collaborators (e.g. technology and software providers, equipment manufacturers, etc.)
	Industry-driven networks and associations (such as EFFRA, IMS)
Academic and research stakeholders	Influencers within worker-led communities, networks and associations that can advocate the benefits of ARTwin
	Academics, researchers and experts focused on advancing the scientific fields cross-cutting ARTwin (e.g. VR, AR, Artificial Intelligence, Workplace Innovation, User-centred Innovation, Computer Vision, Cloud Technology, etc.)
Governmental/ policy stakeholders and Standardisation Bodies	Related EU-funded projects and initiatives
	European Technology Platforms (such as Manufuture, ECTP, NESSI, EPoSS, etc.)
	National and EU regulators and policy-makers in relevant public authorities (such as industrial committees, ministries and regional councils, etc.)
	EU Institutions and Agencies (e.g. the EC, European Science Foundation, MEPs)
Other stakeholders	Standardisation bodies (e.g. ETSI, Word Wide Web Consortium, ISO/IEC, Khronos Group, etc.)
	General public

4. Channels and tools

Several dissemination channels and tools of the ARTwin project will be utilized for awareness raising and stakeholder engagement throughout the duration of the project and beyond. These channels and tools are presented in the following list:

1. Graphical identity and promotional material
2. Project's web-portal and partners' web-portals
3. Project's social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube) and partners' social media accounts
4. Online newsletters
5. Publications
6. Participation in external events
7. ARTwin workshops
8. ARTwin Final Conference
9. Synergies with relevant initiatives and Standardisation Bodies
10. EU dissemination channels

The assets of the project will be distributed through the aforementioned channels and tools to all targeted groups. This process will involve all the activities depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Dissemination, awareness raising and communication activities

All partners will actively participate and contribute to the dissemination and stakeholder engagement efforts both at organization as well as individual level.

4.1 Graphical identity and promotional material

The creation of a graphical identity and promotional material is key for enabling the effective dissemination of the project and its activities. Promotional material will be used both at project workshops and external events, where ARTwin partners participate. Also, it will be used in the everyday publicity of the project.

In compliance with the EU requirements on dissemination of results, as set in Grant Agreement number 856994, Article 29, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic), must display the EU emblem with appropriate prominence and also include the following text: *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 856994”*. In applications for protecting results (including patent applications), the following text must be included: *“The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 856994”*.

In reports and deliverables of public dissemination level, the following disclaimer must also be included: *“The current report reflects only the author’s view and the ARTwin Consortium and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains”*. All obligations, requirements and consequences of no-compliance stated in the Grant Agreement can be found in Annex I.

With that in mind, the main promotional material of the ARTwin project is described in the following subsections. Each partner will be responsible for translations (if considered necessary) and printing of the material according to its specific needs. **Partners should not produce any kind of promotional material, related to the project, without the previous review and approval of WP6 leader, Q-PLAN.**

4.1.1 Logo

ARTwin’s logo was developed in the beginning of the project (M1) and has been approved by all partners.

Figure 2. ARTwin’s logo

4.1.2 Leaflets and posters

A project leaflet and a poster presenting general information on the project (aim, objectives, partners, etc.) will be created by M4 of the project. Apart from the general project leaflet and posters, specific printable promotional material for the promotion of ARTwin events and use cases schemes (e.g. fact sheets, etc.) will be prepared during the project, according to the needs of the partners.

4.1.3 Templates

Templates have been created for the consortium partners to be able to produce their project deliverables and their presentations. In particular, a template for the project’s deliverables (both internal and public) as well as a template for the partners’ presentations have been created and made available to project partners.

Figure 3. ARTwin deliverables' templates

4.1.4 Videos

A short video presenting ARTwin project will be produced so as to create awareness and efficiently boost the dissemination activities. The video will emphasize on promoting the project’s results along with their value propositions as well as our demonstration activities. The preparation of the video is the responsibility of Q-PLAN. The video will be uploaded onto the YouTube channel of the project, that will be created later in the project and well before the publication of the video.

Apart from the promotional video, 3 more videos will be produced showcasing the usefulness of the ARTwin platform in the context of the project’s 3 pilot use cases. In particular, we will develop:

1. A video demonstrating the “AR enabled factory worker” use case in a Siemens factory
2. A video demonstrating the “Dynamic production line planning” use case in a Siemens factory
3. A video demonstrating the “Better constructions with AR” use case in the Eiffage Bretagne construction in Dinard, France

4.2 ARTwin’s web portal and partners’ web portals

The project’s web portal will be developed by M4 of the project (January 2020) and it will constitute the main gateway to ARTwin’s activities, deliverables, news and events. The web portal will contain information about the project’s concept and objectives, the ARTwin platform along with its services, the consortium and the Advisory Board, the project’s 3 use cases, the most recent and active related projects, as well as project’s news. Links to social media accounts of the project and to project partners’ webpages will also be included. As the project evolves, the web portal will be further enriched with all publishable deliverables and promotional material.

The news section of the ARTwin’s web-portal will be updated at least once in a month, according to the availability of news and the web-portal will also be equipped with an online subscription tool for visitors in order to subscribe to the project’s newsletter. ARTwin’s web portal will be available for at least five years after the period of the grant.

Q-PLAN is responsible for the design, operation and update of the project’s web-portal. All partners are required to create links to the project web-portal on their websites and to contribute with the news to be uploaded, as well as to publish occasionally news of the project to the web-portals of their organizations. The ARTwin’s portal will be mentioned in all publicity material generated by the project Consortium.

4.3 Social media networks

The creation of a Facebook page, a LinkedIn page, a Twitter account and a YouTube channel is considered as a key to the communication of the project’s news, events and outcomes. To this end, all social media accounts have been created in M2 of the project (November 2019), except from the YouTube channel which will be created later in the project.

Table 3. ARTwin’s social media accounts

Social Media Platform	ARTwin’s URL
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ARTwin-Project-110545737082313/
Twitter	https://twitter.com/ArtwinProject
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/artwin-project/about/

The project’s social media will be continuously updated in English with news about the project’s activities and results, various events, scientific news, news from several organizations / associations that promote the integration of interactive technologies in industry and construction, news from related EU projects etc.

A YouTube channel will be created later in the project and well before M34, when the promotional videos of the final demonstrators will be developed and made available online. Besides the videos demonstrating the ARTwin’s 3 use cases, a promotional video will be uploaded on the project’s YouTube channel and emphasize on promoting the project’s results along with their value propositions.

Q-PLAN is responsible for the administration of the ARTwin’s social media accounts. All partners are required to become members or/and followers of the social media accounts, to actively like the social media posts of

the project, to disseminate our posts through their personal networks, as well as to publish posts and news about ARTwin regularly, through the social media of their organizations.

4.4 Online newsletter and mailing list

An online newsletter will be prepared and distributed through MailChimp, presenting among others the achieved results, upcoming activities and events, news from similar initiatives and news in the relevant scientific fields. The frequency of newsletter issues will depend on the amount and importance of news to be presented, with the target to produce a newsletter at least every 6 months, however additional ad-hoc newsletters may be added if deemed necessary.

The newsletter recipients' list will be continuously updated during the project, as everyone who is interested will be able to subscribe to the recipients' list by registering on the newsletter section of the project's website. The recipients' list may also be used for the dissemination of other news and announcements related to the project activities.

The newsletter issues will be prepared by Q-PLAN, with the contribution of all partners regarding the content. The content of each issue will be decided and agreed among the consortium. Partners are also required to disseminate the newsletter issues through their own dissemination channels.

4.5 Publications

Both scientific (articles in scientific journals / conferences) and non-scientific (press releases, blogs, etc.) publications will be produced during the project by all project partners. Scientific knowledge generated during the project will be shared in scientific conferences and open access journals. All partners are responsible for identifying any publishing opportunities and for carrying out all necessary actions to ensure publications of project results. All partners do not have the same capacity regarding publications, therefore each partner will undertake the kind of publication (scientific or non-scientific) that is deemed as more suitable. Each partner will make effort to produce publications in the highest quality, which not only reflects on the consortiums' reputation but also on the ARTwin initiative. All publications must cite or/and refer to the EU contribution and project grant agreement number, as required in the Article 29 of the Grant Agreement no 856994. The requirements for scientific publications are available in Annex I. The second sheet of the "ARTwin_dissemination_activities.xls" table, named "Publications" will be used for keeping track of completed publications. The form of the document is shown in Annex II.

4.5.1 *Open access to scientific publication and relevant repositories*

All peer reviewed publications will be deposited either with green open access (i.e. the author, or a representative, archives the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in an online repository before, at the same time as, or after publication), or with gold open access (an article is immediately published in open access mode and the payment of publication costs is shifted away from subscribing readers), according to the ["Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020"](#).

The ARTwin consortium will ensure visibility of the public knowledge lying in public deliverables, open data and scientific publications by sharing them on other widely used platforms and repositories (e.g. Zenodo, OpenAIRE, EFFRA innovation portal, etc.), besides the project's website and social media.

4.6 Participation in external events

The partners of the ARTwin consortium will participate in several external events (at least 30) with the aim to boost the dissemination of project's activities and results. The targeted events, both scientific and business, will relate to the knowledge fields of the project, the sectors it covers as well as the interests of the project's primary stakeholders. The goal is to keep in touch with the latest advances in the research and industry across Europe, share knowledge with respective communities, and establish contacts and interactions with key stakeholders, while at the same time communicating the results of the project. Partners participating in external events (exhibitions, business events, information days, scientific events and conferences) should disseminate the ARTwin project following the guidelines below:

- Before the event, it is necessary to complete "ARTwin_future_events.xls" with the required information about the event. The table can be found in Annex III.
- If a partner is making a presentation, it is requested to use the ARTwin presentation template.
- During the event, it is important to disseminate the project's promotional material (leaflets, etc.).
- A number of photos must be taken.
- The partner is requested to update the Dissemination and Communication Manager about the participation in the event and to share the photos taken, not later than ten days after the event.
- All partners are asked to complete the third sheet of the "ARTwin_dissemination_activities.xls", named "External Events" with all required information about the participation in the event at the latest three weeks after the event. The table can be found in Annex II.

All activities implemented towards the participation of external events as well as their results will be reported in the deliverable D6.4 "Results of dissemination and communication activities – Initial version" (M18) as well as in its updated version, namely D6.7 "Results of dissemination and communication activities – Final version" (M36).

4.7 ARTwin workshops

During the project, two workshops will take place dedicated to familiarizing end-users with the ARTwin platform. The workshops will be organised along with the pilots, by SIE and ART respectively, and they will include demo sessions so as to showcase the project's benefits, gather end-user feedback for further improvements, as well as investigate the interest for the commercial exploitation of the ARTwin solution. Local dissemination campaigns for the workshops will be under the responsibility of the organizer partner, with the support of Q-PLAN for central level dissemination (project web-portal and social media, newsletter and massive e-mail sender tool for dispatch of invitations, press release in English, and promotional material in English). All activities implemented under those workshops as well as their results will be reported in the "Results of dissemination and communication activities" (deliverables D6.4 and updated version D6.7).

4.8 ARTwin Final Conference

By the end of the project, a Final Conference will take place, organized by all project partners under the lead of Q-PLAN and it will probably be organized as satellite at a larger international event. The aim of the conference will be to spread the accumulated knowledge and present the final achievements to scientists, industry, policy makers and generally to all interested parties, with a view to fostering industrial and research utilisation of the project results, as well as contribution to standards. ARTwin's partners should contribute to further disseminate the final event through their personal networks. All activities implemented towards the organization of this conference will be reported in the second version of the "Results of dissemination and communication activities" (deliverable D6.7).

4.9 Synergies with relevant initiatives and Standardisation Bodies

Synergies with other relevant EU-funded or international initiatives will be pursued by all partners in project's research domains and industry sectors, to facilitate knowledge exchange, to gain mutual dissemination benefits and to exploit potential cooperations.

Possible synergies may comprise of participation in events of similar projects, dissemination of ARTwin's promotional material in events of similar projects, invitations to participate in ARTwin's events, exchange of news through each project's channels, inclusion of the project's web-portal and social media as links in websites and social media of other projects, provision of feedback in each project's activities, etc. A "Relevant initiatives" sheet has already been created by Q-PLAN and is part of the "ARTwin_informative_lists.xls" document. The form of this document can be found in Annex III.

Project partners should keep track of all similar projects and initiatives which might be interested in collaboration and should regularly enrich the list. All partners should keep in mind that the ARTwin dissemination strategy cannot reach its full potential unless meaningful collaboration with related projects is established.

Alongside, ARTwin partners, and mainly BCM and SIE, will seek to actively contribute to the activity Standardisation Bodies, with a view to fostering a growing and sustainable AR ecosystem across Europe, all while enhancing the brand of the ARTwin project and its solutions.

4.10 EU dissemination channels

The following EU dissemination channels are going to be used during the project:

- **EIT Digital and EIT Manufacturing.** EIT Digital and EIT Manufacturing support the development of dynamic pan-European partnerships among leading companies, research and academia dedicated to finding solutions for digitalization and efficient manufacturing across Europe respectively.
- **European Enterprise Network (EEN).** The EEN is an EU network of around 600 business support organizations from more than 60 countries, including chambers of commerce and industry, technology centers, research institutes and development agencies.

- **European Cooperation in Science and Technology.** The cooperation connects research initiatives across Europe and enables researchers and innovators to grow their ideas in technology by sharing them with peers.
- **European Science Foundation.** ESF is committed to promoting highest quality science in Europe to drive progress in research and innovation.
- **CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service) WIRE.** CORDIS WIRE is a CORDIS online service that helps research and business community to promote projects' activities by publishing news and events on CORDIS.
- **EU industry days and info-days, workshops and conferences.**

The Project Officer will be contacted with regards to possible dissemination steps supported by the EU.

5. Publicity timetable

Table 4. Action plan for the dissemination, awareness raising and communication activities

Activity	Partner	WP	'19	'20				'21				'22								
			Oct. – Nov.	Dec.-Jan.	Feb. – Mar.	Apr. – May	June- July	Aug. – Sep.	Oct.- Nov.	Dec.-Jan.	Feb. – Mar.	April – May	June- July	Aug. – Sep.	Oct.- Nov.	Dec.-Jan.	Feb. – Mar.	Apr. – May	June- July	Aug. – Sep.
Development of promotional material																				
Logo	Q-PLAN	WP6																		
Template	Q-PLAN	All WPs																		
Leaflet, poster	Q-PLAN	WP6																		
Videos	Q-PLAN	WP6																		
Web portal																				
Development of web portal	Q-PLAN	WP6																		
Publicity through web portal	All partners	All WPs																		
Publicity through partners' web portals	All partners	All WPs																		
Social media networks																				
Creation of social media accounts	Q-PLAN	WP6																		
Publicity through projects' social media	All partners	All WPs																		
Publicity through partners' social media	All partners	All WPs																		

Activity	Partner	WP	'19	'20				'21				'22								
			Oct. – Nov.	Dec.-Jan.	Feb. – Mar.	Apr. – May	June-July	Aug. – Sep.	Oct. – Nov.	Dec.-Jan.	Feb. – Mar.	April – May	June-July	Aug. – Sep.	Oct. – Nov.	Dec.-Jan.	Feb. – Mar.	Apr. – May	June-July	Aug. – Sep.
Creation and publicity through YouTube channel	Q-PLAN	WP6																		
Online Newsletter																				
Mailing list formation	Q-PLAN	WP6																		
E - newsletter	Q-PLAN	WP6																		
Publications																				
Non – scientific publications	All partners	WP2-																		
Scientific publications	All partners	WP2-																		
External events																				
Exhibitions, business events, information days etc.	All partners	WP6																		
Scientific events, conferences etc.	All partners	WP6																		
Project's workshops																				
1 st Workshop	Q-PLAN, SIE	WP5																		
2 nd Workshop	Q-PLAN, ART	WP5																		
Final conference																				
ARTwin Final Conference	All partners	All WPs																		
Synergies with related projects/initiatives																				

Activity	Partner	WP	'19	'20				'21				'22								
			Oct. – Nov.	Dec.-Jan.	Feb. – Mar.	Apr. - May	June-July	Aug. – Sep.	Oct.- Nov.	Dec.-Jan.	Feb. – Mar.	April - May	June-July	Aug. – Sep.	Oct.- Nov.	Dec.-Jan.	Feb. – Mar.	Apr. - May	June-July	Aug. – Sep.
Establishment of synergies with relevant initiatives	Q-PLAN, All	WP6																		
EU dissemination channels																				
EIT Digital, EIT Manufacturing, CORDIS WIRE, EEN, ESF	Q-PLAN	WP6																		

Beyond the end of the project, partners are committed to continue disseminating the project’s outcomes through their everyday activities, networks and means of communication employed to reach related stakeholder groups. The stakeholders that will have participated in the activities of the project are expected to act as multipliers of the ARTwin’s results beyond its lifespan.

6. Performance indicators and monitoring

To measure the success of ARTwin’s awareness raising and communication strategy, the following KPIs will be employed and all dissemination activities along with their results will be monitored and compared to these KPIs, so as to assess whether ARTwin is on the right path or if alternative dissemination efforts need to take place.

Table 5. Dissemination and communication impact indicators

Indicator (KPI)	Target Value (Impact)
Number of Scientific papers published	12 (in scientific conferences and journals)
Number of external events / conferences attended	30 events / conferences (research and industrial)
Synergies with major initiatives and networks	10 joint actions
Number of visits to the ARTwin web portal	12,000 unique visitors by the end of the project
Number of followers in the social media accounts	2,000 followers (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube)
Number of promotional materials distributed	2,000 copies distributed in project/ external events
Number of newsletters	6 newsletters (one per semester)
Number of workshops/ participants in each one	2 workshops/ 30 participants per workshop
Number of participants in the Final Conference	100 participants
Interactive technology and solution providers engaged	>100

To meet these target values, project partners are expected to continuously carry out publicity actions and continuously report all outcomes. Q-PLAN will be overall responsible for the monitoring and evaluation of ARTwin’s dissemination activities.

Reporting of any dissemination activity and publication is expected from partners by completing the “ARTwin_dissemination_activities.xls” document and sending it to WP6 leader Q-PLAN, at the latest three weeks after the dissemination activity or publication. Especially for participation in external events, partners should follow the respective guidelines (see section 4.6). In the case of events organized by the project, the partner responsible for the organization of the event must prepare an Event Report, in the form of Annex IV, at the latest three weeks after the dissemination activity or publication.

Partners should produce no kind of promotional material related to the project without the previous review and approval of WP6 leader Q-PLAN. Each project partner should immediately contact Q-PLAN if they identify opportunities, problems or risks arising while planning or implementing publicity actions.

7. Conclusions

This document, titled “Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan”, provided the framework and guidelines for the successful implementation of dissemination, awareness raising and communication activities throughout the lifespan of the project and beyond. The plan addressed what to disseminate, to whom, by what means and when, as well as provided the monitoring framework that will be used for assessing the dissemination activities, which is based on targeted KPIs.

By communicating the project’s tangible and intangible assets through the most effective channels and tools to timely reach the targeted groups, ARTwin will be able to not only go beyond its ambitious KPIs but most importantly to lay the foundations for the successful rollout, replication and thus sustainability of its outcomes.

As the project evolves, the dissemination, awareness raising and communication plan will be updated and refined (“D6.5 Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan – Final version”, M18), in order to provide a more detailed analysis of the dissemination actions that will take place, in order to maximize the visibility and outreach of the ARTwin’s solutions.

Annexes

Annex I – EU requirements

ARTICLE 29 of GA 856994 — DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS — OPEN ACCESS — VISIBILITY OF EU FUNDING

29.1 Obligation to disseminate results

Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium). This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply. A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests.

If a beneficiary intends not to protect its results, it may — under certain conditions (see Article 26.4.1)— need to formally notify the Commission before dissemination takes place.

29.2 Open access to scientific publications

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, it must:

(a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications; Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

(b) ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:

(i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or

(ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.

(c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and

- a persistent identifier.

29.3 Open access to research data

Regarding the digital research data generated in the action (**'data'**), the beneficiaries must:

(a) deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user — the following:

(i) the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible;

(ii) not applicable;

(iii) other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the 'data management plan' (see Annex 1 of Grant Agreement no 856994);

(b) provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves).

This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.

As an exception, the beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their research data under Point (a)(i) and (iii), if the achievement of the action's main objective (as described in Annex 1 of Grant Agreement no 856994) would be jeopardized by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible. In this case, the data management plan must contain the reasons for not giving access.

29.4 Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

(a) display the EU emblem and

(b) include the following text:

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 856994".

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Commission. This does not however give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

29.5 Disclaimer excluding Commission responsibility

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

29.6 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 43). Such a breach may also lead to any of the other measures described in Chapter 6.

Annex II - Dissemination activities list

Dissemination activities

Type of activity	Partner	Title	Date	Channel / Place	Type of audience	Size of audience	Countries addressed

Publications

Authors	Proceedings	Date of publication	Start date of Conference	Publisher	Publisher location	ISBN	URL	Relevant pages	Open access

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External events

Event	Participating partner	Date	Venue	Organiser	Link	Type of audience	Size of audience	Distributed material

Annex III – Informative lists

Future events

Event	Date	Venue	Organiser	Link

Stakeholders list

Stakeholder	Type of Stakeholder	Sector	Website	Country	Partner with contact	Comments

Relevant initiatives

Initiative	Type of initiative (H2020 project, network, etc.)	Website	Partner with contact	Comments

EU dissemination channels

Activity	Partner	Organisation	Website	Comments

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Annex IV - Event report

Event name

Event date

Event venue

Event Report

Event Organising Partner	<Insert Partner name>
Authors	Name of Author 1
	Name of Author 2
	Name of Author 3

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